

Identification of polar bioactive substances in the Upper Rhine using effect-directed analysis

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ABSTRACT

Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) was used to identify bioactive compounds in surface and well water from the Upper Rhine, and to evaluate their properties against the criteria set for Persistent, Mobile and Toxic (PMT) and very persistent and very mobile (vPvM) substances. A multi-layered solid-phase extraction was implemented to enrich a broad range of polar substances from the collected samples. The extracts were fractionated into 108 fractions and tested in the transthyretin (TTR)-binding assay measuring displacement of fluorescently labeled thyroxine (FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay) and the *Aliivibrio fischeri* bioluminescence (AFB) bioassay. Bioactive fractions guided the identification strategy using high-resolution mass spectrometry. Chemical features were systematically annotated using library databases and suspect lists, incorporating an automated assessment of the quality of each annotation. Based on this assessment, each chemical feature was assigned a specific identification confidence level. Identification of bioactive compounds was facilitated by using bioassay specific suspect lists that were extracted from an in-house developed database of positive and negative TTR-binding compounds and from a recently published database of active inhibitors of AFB. This resulted in the identification and confirmation of ten bioactive substances, including four evaluated as PMT and vPvM substances (diclofenac, trifloxystrobin acid, 6:2 FTSA and PFOA), and one as a potential PMT substance (4-aminoazobenzene). This study demonstrates the effectiveness of EDA in the identification of PMT/vPvM substances in the aquatic environment, facilitating their prioritization for comprehensive environmental risk assessment and possible regulation.

1. Introduction

The presence of bioactive chemicals in environmental waters is a growing concern due to their potential effects on ecosystems and human health (Posthuma et al., 2020). These chemicals, which originate from diverse industrial, agricultural, and urban sources, can interact with biological systems in significant ways (Cumming et al., 2014). Over the last years, Persistent, Mobile and Toxic (PMT) substances, as well as very Persistent and very Mobile (vPvM) substances, in drinking water sources have received increasing attention in environmental monitoring programs (Scheurer et al., 2022; Rüdél et al., 2020; Neuwald et al., 2022). Persistent substances are characterized by their resistance to biodegradation in the environment (Hale et al., 2022), leading to their prolonged presence over long periods of time. Mobile substances, characterized by

their polar properties, are able to pass through soil, ground water and artificial barriers due to high water solubility and low sorption. Therefore, substances with combined persistent and mobile properties can stay in water for extended periods (Hale et al., 2022), and simultaneously can travel considerable distances through various aqueous environments such as wastewater treatment plants, subsurface and even drinking water treatment systems (Reemtsma et al., 2016; Arp and Hale, 2022). The unrestricted release of PMT/vPvM substances can lead to their gradual accumulation in the environment (Reemtsma et al., 2016), highlighting the importance of recognizing and addressing the potential risks associated with these compounds. To address this concern, the European Commission has recently introduced new hazard criteria for PMT/vPvM substances (European Commission 2023).

A comprehensive strategy to identify and characterize emerging

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substances in environmental samples, including PMT/vPvM substances, is to perform suspect and non-target screening (SNTS) based on liquid chromatography high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) (Hollender et al., 2017). The SNTS methodology has significantly developed and expanded in recent years with the creation of multiple open-source (Helmus et al., 2021; Feraud et al., 2023) and commercial software tools (MS SOFTWARE MetaboScape®; Brochure 2023) for peak picking and data processing. PMT/vPvM and other emerging substances can be tentatively identified (Schymanski et al., 2014; Alygizakis et al., 2023; Jonkers et al., 2022) using libraries of experimental MS/MS spectra (MassBank/MassBank-Data; Massbank of North America), various suspect lists (NORMAN Network NORMAN Suspect List Exchange (NORMAN-SLE), and predictive tools (Ruttkies et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2021; Aalizadeh et al., 2021). To prioritize features for identification and subsequent confirmation, the toxicological hazard of the annotated features can be considered through the CompTox Chemicals Dashboard (CompTox Chemicals Dashboard: Release Notes | US EPA) and Cheminformatics analysis modules (Cheminformatics Modules) or through recently developed machine learning-based hazard-driven prioritization tools (Arturi and Hollender, 2023). These computational approaches allow features to be prioritized for identification and subsequent confirmation, but in some cases, only a prediction of the possible hazard of the prioritized substances is given. Consequently, the risk assessment is more complex as the exact hazard of the substances is unknown.

Alternatively, Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) may be used as an effective experiment-driven prioritization tool (Brack et al., 2016). In EDA, sample extracts are tested in bioassays and chemical identification is focused on the features related to the measured activity. In principle the extract is fractionated to reduce the chemical complexity and chemical features are only considered for identification if they are related to the measured activity. EDA is very useful for the identification of bioactive chemicals that are present in the tested samples in sufficient quantities to cause a bioassay response (Jonkers et al., 2023).

In the context of EDA, selecting appropriate bioassays is a critical aspect. Compounds that are bioactive in one bioassay, may show no activity in another bioassay. In order to identify a wide spectrum of bioactive compounds, two bioassays indicative for completely different modes of action were used in the present study. The transthyretin (TTR)-binding assays (Ren and Guo, 2012; Leusch et al., 2018) are increasingly utilized (Jonkers et al., 2022; Behnisch et al., 2021; de Schepper et al., 2023; Mikusova et al., 2024; Hamers et al., 2020; Weiss et al., 2009; Langberg et al., 2023) to detect substances that specifically compete with the thyroid hormone thyroxine (T4) for binding to its transport protein TTR. Such compounds may disrupt delivery of T4 to target tissues, including the developing brain (Johansson et al., 2008) that is highly dependent on an adequate supply of thyroid hormones (Korevaar et al., 2016). The *Aliivibrio fischeri* bioluminescence (AFB) bioassay (Abbas et al., 2018) is a rapid and sensitive bioassay that is often used to evaluate potential hazards of substances in environmental samples (Abbas et al., 2018). The AFB bioassay responds to chemicals that inhibit bacterial bioluminescence, which is a generic indicator of multiple cellular processes involved in bacterial respiration and energy production that can be disturbed.

The goal of the present study was to identify polar substances in surface water from the Rhine River and its corresponding well water used as raw water for drinking water production using EDA. Identified substances were prioritized based on their bioactivity in the TTR-binding and AFB bioassay and were further assessed for their PMT/vPvM properties according to the criteria set by Arp and Hale (2022). This study is the first of its kind to demonstrate how EDA can be combined with PMT/vPvM assessment as a strategy to identify and prioritize emerging potential PMT/vPvM substances for comprehensive environmental risk assessment and possible regulation.

In addition, a comprehensive database of active and inactive compounds in the TTR-binding assays based on existing data (Ren and Guo,

2012; Leusch et al., 2018; Hamers et al., 2020; Weiss et al., 2009; Langberg et al., 2023; Cao et al., 2010; Chauhan et al., 2000; Cheek et al., 1999; Gales et al., 2008; Grimm et al., 2013; Hamers et al., 2011; Hamers et al., 2006; Hamers et al., 2008; Hill et al., 2018; Lans et al., 1993; Marchesini et al., 2008; Marchesini et al., 2006; Meerts, 2000; Montañó et al., 2012; Munro et al., 1989; Qin et al., 2019; Ren et al., 2016; Rickenbacher et al., 1986; Simon et al., 2011; Simon et al., 2013; Ucán-Marin et al., 2010; van den Berg, 1990; Viluksela et al., 2014; Weiss et al., 2015; Xi et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2015; Huang et al., 2023) was developed. This database was used to create a specific suspect list of TTR-binding compounds to facilitate the identification of compounds that may cause disruption of the thyroid hormone system in humans and other species.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples and sampling

Surface (SW) and well water (WW) samples from the Rhine River were collected in the Mainz-Bingen district of Rhineland-Palatinate (Germany) in glass amber 2.5 L bottles in March 2023. Atmospheric temperature was 5 °C and humidity level of 85 %. These water samples were transported chilled and stored at 4 °C until sample preparation. The water is heavily impacted by numerous sewage treatment plants and emissions from industrial areas located upstream. SW was a grab sample, and WW was collected from the pipe of a drinking water production plant.

2.2. Multi-layered solid phase extraction and validation

Multi-layered solid phase extraction (MSPE) cartridges were prepared manually according to the methods described by Ruff et al. (2015) and Mechelke et al. (2019), and consisted of a bottom layer of 200-mg of ENVI-carb™ (Supelco, USA), a middle layer of 350-mg of a 1:1:1.5 (w/w/w) mixture of Strata X-AW, Strata X-CW (both: Phenomenex, USA), and Isolute ENV+ (Biotage AB, Sweden), and a top layer of 200 mg Oasis HLB (Waters, USA). The SPE procedure itself was performed with some modifications. In short, the water samples (2L per sample) were centrifuged at 3000 rpm (Froilabo Firlabo SW12, France) and aliquoted into two 1 L bottles. The samples were adjusted to pH 6.6 by adding 1 mL of 1 M ammonium acetate buffer and 40 µL of formic acid (>99 %). The multi-layered (ML) cartridges were conditioned sequentially with 10 mL methanol, 10 mL acetonitrile, and 20 mL of Milli-Q water. Each 1 L aliquot of water was loaded on a separate multi-layered cartridge. Elution was performed in the back flush mode (cartridges were turned upside down) with 6 mL of methanol/ethyl acetate (v/v, 1:1) containing 2 % (v/v) ammonia (25 %), 3 mL of methanol/ethyl acetate (v/v 1:1) containing 1.7 % (v/v) formic acid (>99 %) followed by 2 mL of methanol into one conical vessel resulting in a combined neutral extract. The cartridges were eluted in back flush mode to avoid substances to get permanently absorbed by the black carbon. The extracts were evaporated to a volume of 100 µL at 25 °C with a nitrogen flow rate of 1.5 mL/min in a nitrogen evaporator (Biotage, TurboVap). The two extracts from the same sample were combined together in one collection vial resulting in a total volume of 200 µL. Subsequently, 50 µL of methanol was added to the vessels, which were vortexed for 2 min. This was followed by the addition of 250 µL of Milli-Q water, and the mixture was vortexed again for 3 min. This mixture was transferred to the collection vial, resulting in a 500 µL solution with an enrichment factor of 4000 (2L/(500 L*10⁻⁶)). The same procedure was applied to 2 L Milli-Q water, which served as a procedural blank (PB).

For the brief verification of the MSPE performance, the following procedure was performed according to Mechelke et al. (2019). Each sample (SW and WW) was split into three aliquots, which were all three

spiked (0.05 ng/mL) with twelve labelled standards (Table S1). Before SPE-extraction, the first aliquot was additionally spiked (0.25 ng/mL) with nineteen non-labelled M and vM substances (Table S1). These substances covered a broad range of LogD values (from -5.2 to 2.8) and included various classes of PM substances often found in water, such as triazines, triazoles, PFAS, and various antibiotics (Arp and Hale, 2022). The second aliquot was extracted using SPE and the extracts were subsequently spiked (1 ug/mL) with the same nineteen non-labelled substances. The third aliquot was extracted using SPE and was not spiked with the non-labelled substances. In case substances were also found in unspiked samples (the third aliquot), their peak areas were subtracted from the peak areas in the first (pre-spike) and second (post spike) aliquots.

Recovery was calculated according to the following equation:

$$\text{Recovery, \%} = (S_{\text{pre-spike}} \times S_{\text{IS2}}) / (S_{\text{IS1}} \times S_{\text{post-spike}}) \quad (1)$$

where $S_{\text{pre-spike}}$ – peak area of the non-labelled standard in the extract of the sample that was spiked before SPE; $S_{\text{post-spike}}$ – peak area of the non-labelled standard in the extract that was spiked after SPE; S_{IS1} – peak area of the labelled standard in the extract of the sample that was spiked before SPE with non-labelled standards; S_{IS2} – peak area of the labelled standard in the extract of the sample that was spiked after SPE with non-labelled standards

2.3. LC-HRMS analysis and fractionations

LC-HRMS analysis of the extracts was performed on an Agilent 1290 Infinity HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Amstelveen, The Netherlands) coupled to a Bruker Daltonics Compact II QTOF mass spectrometer (Bruker, Bremen, Germany). The extracts were separated on an XSelect HSS T3 column (Waters, 150 mm × 2.1 mm, 2.5 μm) set at 40 °C. Milli-Q with 0.1 % formic acid (A) and methanol with 0.1 % formic acid (B) were used as mobile phase solvents, and the flow rate was 500 μL/min. The following gradient of the mobile phases was applied: 0 to 1.5 min 1 % B, 1.5 to 12 min 1–50 % B, 12 to 18 min 50–99 % B, 18 to 25 min 99 % B, 25 to 26 min 99–1 % B, 26 to 33 min 1 % B. The injection volume was 20 μL.

HRMS analysis was performed using electrospray ionization (ESI) in positive and negative ion modes. Full-scan (MS) and data dependent acquisition (DDA) MS/MS scans were recorded from 50 to 1300 *m/z* at spectra rates of 2 Hz (MS) and 5 Hz (MS/MS), respectively. Ion source parameters were as follows: End Plate Offset 500 V, Capillary 4500 V (positive mode) and 3500 V (negative mode), Nebulizer 3 bar, Dry gas 9 L/min, and Dry temp 300 °C. MS/MS data acquisition was performed according to Jonkers et al. (2022). Mass measurements were calibrated by injecting a tuning mix (sodium formate) at the beginning of each sample injection.

Fractionation was performed with a FractioMate™ fraction collector (SPARKHolland, Emmen & VU Amsterdam, the Netherlands) using the same HPLC conditions as described above. The effluent from the column was fractionated into 108 wells in two 96-well plates (54 wells each, Figure S1) of the respective bioassay (positions B3-G11) that were pre-filled with 10 μL of keeper solvent (10 % DMSO in Milli-Q) for the TTR-binding assay measuring displacement of fluorescently labeled thyroxine (FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay) and 5 μL of the same solution for the AFB bioassay. Fractionations for the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay were performed in black 96-wells polystyrene nonbinding plates (Greiner Bio-One) and for AFB bioassay in white Greiner Lumitrack plates (Greiner Bio-One). Each fraction corresponded to a 13.5 s interval of the LC-run. An error margin, which addresses a delay between the retention times (t_R) of the fractionated plates and the MS measurements, was set at 9 s (Section S1.1). After fraction collection, the well plates were dried in a CentriVap concentrator (Labconco, Kansas City, United States) under vacuum for approximately 4.5 h at 25 °C. The evaporated plates were reconstituted in the final volume of 200 μL for the FITC-T4

TTR-binding assay (Section S1.2) and 100 μL for the AFB bioassay (Section S1.3). Thus, the resulting relative enrichment factor (REF) in the fractionated plates for the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay was 400 and for AFB bioassay 800, under the assumption that each compound elutes in one single fraction. Fractionation was performed once per assay, due to the limited amount of the sample extract and good reproducibility of the fractionation, described earlier (Jonkers et al., 2022).

The background contamination of the system and the stability of the retention times were assessed by injecting a solvent blank and a mixture of standards (Table S1), which were injected three times before fractionation, three times after fractionation (i.e. before the LC-MS analysis) and after the LC-MS analysis.

2.4. In-vitro bioassays

The FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay and AFB bioassay were performed first on the unfractionated extracts to verify if they are relevant for the samples. Unfractionated extracts were tested in four dilutions ($n = 2$ for FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay and $n = 4$ for AFB bioassay). Prior to the testing in the bioassay, the unfractionated extracts (20 uL) were evaporated in a CentriVap concentrator (Labconco, Kansas City, United States) at 25 °C under vacuum and reconstituted in 20 uL of DMSO.

2.4.1. FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay

The FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay makes use of a conjugate of the thyroid hormone thyroxine (T4) and a fluorescent marker called fluorescein 5-isothiocyanate (FITC) (Ren and Guo, 2012). When the T4 part of this FITC-T4 conjugate binds to TTR, the fluorescence of the FITC marker is increased, due to the fact that the bound T4 group causes less intramolecular quenching than the free T4 group. If a substance is capable of displacing FITC-T4 from TTR, the intramolecular quenching is restored and the consequent decrease in fluorescence is a key indicator of the assay. The assay was performed according to Jonkers et al. (2022) and described in detail in Section S1.2. The highest REF tested in the assay was 40 for the unfractionated extracts, and 400 for the fractionated extracts.

2.4.2. AFB bioassay

The AFB bioassay was performed according to (Hamers et al., 2001; Hamers et al., 2018) with some modifications, as described in detail in Section S1.3. The highest REF tested was 20 for the unfractionated extracts, and 800 for the fractionated extracts.

2.4.3. Selection of the bioactive fractions

Bioactive fractions for the AFB bioassay were distinguished from background noise by comparing the activity of the individual fraction normalized to the response of the PB to a hit threshold that was set at 20 % luminescence inhibition.

Bioactive fractions in the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay were identified using a generalized additive model (GAM) according to Jonkers et al. (2023). In short, a bioactive fraction was identified based on its bioassay response, which needs to significantly differ from that of PB. The GAM was utilized to adjust for biases potentially introduced due to the consistent plate location of each fraction across samples. This model was fitted to the bioassay chromatogram of PB. By considering the residuals of the GAM, which were corrected for variations attributed to fraction number and plate position, a standard deviation for PB was calculated. This standard deviation reflected both the biological variation inherent in the bioassay and the measurement error. Fractions within the sample extracts were deemed bioactive if their bioassay signal deviated from the model's predictions by at least 3 times the standard deviation.

2.5. TTR-binding database, TTR-binding and AFB bioassay suspect lists

A database was constructed including 433 unique compounds that were tested for their TTR-binding potency and for which an IC₅₀ and/or

a TTR-binding potency relative to T4 were reported in open literature. An overview of the different studies included in the database, together with their number of test compounds and method of TTR-binding measurements is provided in Table S2. The database was curated into a suspect list that was used to annotate features from HRMS data. Both database and suspect list are provided in the [supplementary Excel S1](#) file. To produce the suspect list, structural information of the compounds was collected in the form of simplified molecular-input line-entry system (SMILES) strings. Duplicates and compounds that showed no TTR-binding activity were removed and the remaining entries were standardized to create “MS-ready” structures according to the modified KNIME workflow of [McEachran et al. \(2018\)](#), as was presented by [Meijer et al. \(2021\)](#). Subsequently, molecular formulas, “MS-ready” SMILES and InChIKeys were produced from the “MS-ready” structures using the Indigo nodes for KNIME ([Indigo Nodes for KNIME | KNIME](#)) and the monoisotopic-, protonated- $[M + H]^+$ and deprotonated- $[M - H]^-$ masses were calculated from the molecular formula using the `enviPath` package in R ([Loos et al., 2015](#)). Additional data related to retention time index, ionization, and chromatography platform suitability was collected from the NORMAN SusDat database ([Network et al., 2022](#)) to facilitate the evaluation of annotation plausibility. After the removal of inactive compounds and structure standardization, 250 TTR-binding compounds from the database were included into the suspect list. Metadata related to retention time index, ionization, and chromatography platform suitability was collected for 151 of these compounds.

For the AFB bioassay, a comprehensive database ([Yu et al., 2023](#)) containing 1236 substances, each characterized by their bioactivity, was employed to develop a corresponding suspect list ([Excel S2 file](#)). The approach undertaken for the AFB bioassay suspect list involved a workflow that was consistent with the one applied to the TTR-binding suspect list, as described above.

2.6. Data-processing and identification workflow

The data processing and identification strategy was performed

Fig. 1. Data-processing and identification scheme.

according to [Jonkers et al. \(2022\)](#) (section S1.5) and presented in [Fig. 1](#).

2.7. Confirmation of the identified substances and their activity in the assays

Reference standards were purchased for the tentatively identified substances to confirm their presence in the samples and their activity in the bioassays. Identification was confirmed if the reference compound had the same retention time (± 0.1 min), accurate mass (± 5 ppm), and MS/MS spectra (the same fragment ions and their ratios).

The activity in the bioassay was confirmed if the compound demonstrated a concentration-dependent response in the corresponding bioassay. Data was analysed using GraphPad Prism 8.1.0 (La Jolla, California, United States). The dose-response curves were fitted through the data using the Hill equation:

$$Y = A + (D - A) / \left(1 + (x/EC50)^{hill\ slope} \right) \quad (2)$$

in which A and D represent the minimum and maximum response respectively.

If the activity of a compound was confirmed, its concentration was determined semi-quantitatively using the standard addition method ([Coglianese et al., 2023](#)). In brief, areas of the peaks on the LC-HRMS chromatograms in the extracts of the samples and in the tested solution of the reference substances were compared. Confirmed substances were spiked to the extract of the samples with a concentration that should theoretically (not taking into account possible matrix effect influence) correspond to the same area found in the sample. Then the non-spiked and spiked extracts were analysed. The concentrations of the confirmed substances were calculated as follows:

$$C_{extract} = C_{standard} \times [S_{extract} / (S_{total} - S_{extract})] \quad (3)$$

where $C_{extract}$ – concentration of the substance in the extract; $C_{standard}$ – final spike concentration of the substance after its addition to the extract; $S_{extract}$ – peak area of the substance in the extract; S_{total} – peak area of the substance after spike

2.8. Calculation of the contributions of the identified substances to the bioactive response of the fractions

To determine the contributions of the identified substances to the response of the bioactive fractions, the concept of bioanalytical equivalent concentrations (BEQ) was applied ([Neale et al., 2015](#)). The bioactivity of a sample is expressed as the concentration of a reference compound that induces an equivalent level of bioactivity. In this study, T4 served as the reference compound for the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay and triclosan for the AFB bioassay. For each active fraction, the BEQ value in the bioassay (BEQ_{bio}) was determined by interpolating the measured bioassay response into the dose-response curve of the reference compound (Figure S6). The corresponding BEQ value based on the semi-quantitative concentrations of confirmed active substances (BEQ_{chem}) was calculated by multiplying these concentrations by their corresponding relative potencies (RPs). The RP values for each candidate compound were established by dividing the IC_{20} of the reference compound by the IC_{20} value of each compound in the bioassay. The contributions of the confirmed compounds to the response of the fractions were calculated by dividing the BEQ_{chem} values by the BEQ_{bio} values and then multiplying the result by 100 %.

2.9. PMT/vPvM assessment approach of the identified substances

The PMT/vPvM assessment was done following the workflow presented in studies by [Arp and Hale \(2022\)](#); (2023), and in line with the recent PMT/vPvM criteria put into force by the recent delegated amendment to the EU classification, labelling and packaging (CLP)

regulation (European Commission 2023). In brief, for the substances identified, an assessment of persistent (P) or very persistent (vP) was done to see if there were any simulated environmental half-life data in the literature indicating that the threshold half-lives for P (> 40 days for freshwater, >120 days for soil or sediment) or vP (>60 days for freshwater, >180 days for soil or sediment) were exceeded. If simulated half-life studies were not available, a weight-of-evidence decision was made based on alternative data that could indicate persistence, such as ready biodegradability tests and predictive models (Arp and Hale, 2022). As an example, biodegradability tests indicating ready biodegradable indicate not-persistent; however, substances that are not ready biodegradable and have predictive models that indicate half-live thresholds may be exceeded can be considered “Potential P/vP” subject to further testing. Mobile (M) and very Mobile (vM) were assessed by comparison with the lowest, experimental log organic carbon-water distribution coefficients, $\log K_{OC}$, reported in the literature, between a pH of 4 – 9, where values < 2.0 indicate vM and between 2 and <3.0 indicate M⁹. When $\log K_{OC}$ values were not available, a weight-of-evidence approach based on pH specific log octanol-water distribution coefficients, $\log D$, was used, to differentiate between vM, not M, potential M/vM depending on the ionic charge or ionizability (Arp and Hale, 2022). Based on the results, substances can be either vPvM, PM, Potentially PM/vPvM or not PM. This assessment can be combined with a toxicity assessment, where PM substances exhibiting toxicity (T) are considered PMT, and vPvM substances exhibiting toxicity can be considered vPvM & PMT (European Commission 2023). Toxicity here, according to the EU CLP delegated regulation 2023/707 (section 4.4.2.1.3.), (European Commission 2023) refers to the situation where the substance meets the criteria for classification as carcinogenic (category 1A or 1B), germ cell mutagenic (category 1A or 1B), toxic for reproduction (category 1A, 1B, or 2), specific target organ toxicity after repeated exposure (STOT RE category 1 or 2) or classification as an endocrine disruptor (category 1) for human health or the environment, or exhibits a long-term no-observed effect concentration (NOEC) or ECx (e.g. EC₁₀) for marine or freshwater organisms is < 0.01 mg/L. Just one of these criteria need to be met for the substance to be classified as T. To assess here if the T criteria were met, first the European Chemical Agency’s infocard of substances under consideration were consulted (ECHA) to see if a harmonized classification was given in regard to the aforementioned criteria, with the exception of the NOEC/ECx < 0.01 mg/L. For the latter, a manual literature search was conducted of opinions from the European Commission’s Scientific Committee on Health, Environmental and Emerging Risks (SCHEER) (SCHEER) and the Pesticide Property Database (Lewis et al., 2016).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. MSPE performance

The modified MSPE procedure was verified in a brief recovery validation study (section S2.1). The results of the verification were comparable with the previously described recoveries (Mechelke et al., 2019). A median recovery of 60 % was obtained, which is acceptable considering the non-targeted screening approach (Schulze et al., 2017; Dürig et al., 2020). Our objective was to collect a broader range of compounds with moderate recoveries, rather than focusing on a limited number of compounds with very high recoveries. Despite the considerable sensitivity of the employed bioassays, the pre-concentration step remains indispensable in EDA due to the low concentrations of contaminants found in surface and well water samples ranging from ng/L to ug/L. MSPE (Ruff et al., 2015; Mechelke et al., 2019) appears to be an attractive option for the separation of a wide range of substances with different properties (from hydrophobic to very polar, cationic and anionic) and is highly capable of preconcentrating substances with enrichment factors that can be tailored to the required sensitivity levels. However, MSPE may lead to more blank effects in bioassays compared to

single sorbent SPE due to the combination of multiple sorbets.

3.2. Bioassay results for the unfractionated and fractionated extracts

The unfractionated and fractionated extracts of PB, WW, and SW samples were tested in the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay and AFB bioassay. The extracts demonstrated concentration-dependent activity in FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay (Fig. 2A1) and AFB bioassay (Fig. 2B1), triggering fractionations of these extracts. More active fractions were found for the fractionated SW samples compared to the WW samples in both assays (Figs. 2A2 and 2B2), confirming the observed differences in bioassay responses to the unfractionated extracts.

Following the application of the GAM model on the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay results, 20 fractions exceeded the 3SD threshold for the fitted fluorescence signal of the PB, as detailed in Table S4. Identification efforts were focused on the five fractions of SW and of WW extracts that exhibited the highest inhibition of FITC-T4 binding to TTR. For the SW extract, the highest significant inhibition was found specifically in fractions 66 (80.3 % FITC-T4 binding compared to the negative control), 73 (80.7 %), 82 (78 %), 83 (51 %), and 84 (76.8 %). For the WW extract, the fractions identified with significant inhibition were 65 (80.7 % FITC-T4 binding compared to the negative control), 83 (52.5 %), and 84 (69.6 %). In the AFB bioassay, for SW extract, fractions 5 (74.6 % luminescence compared to the negative control), 71 (75.3 %), and 81 (70.8 %) were classified as active, as they exhibited more than 20 % inhibition in the luminescence signal of bacteria. For WW extract, however, no fractions were identified as active, which is consistent with the results of unfractionated WW extract compared to PB extracts.

3.3. Identification of bioactive compounds at Schymanski levels 2 to 5

Using the semi-automated workflow, the water and oil-repellent perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) was identified (negative mode) in active FITC-T4 TTR-binding fraction 73 at level 2a. PFOA eluted in two chromatographic peaks with a first small peak of tentative branched isomers (Pellizzaro et al., 2018) of PFOA at a retention time (t_R) of 16.71 min and a second peak of the tentative linear isomer (t_R =16.95 min). Taking into account the delay time between MS and fractionations (Section S1.1), only the tentative branched PFOA contributed to the response in the fraction. The surfactant and foam stabilizer 6:2 fluorotelomer sulfonic acid (6:2 FTSA) - another perfluorinated alkylated substance (PFAS) - was identified (negative mode) in fraction 73 at level 3. The non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) diclofenac was also identified (positive and negative ion mode) in fractions 72 and 73 at level 4, due to a match with the TTR-binding suspect list. The RTI platform (Section 2.6) was utilized to evaluate the likelihood of diclofenac eluting at a specific retention time. The predicted t_R =16.87 min for diclofenac, closely aligned with the experimental t_R =16.66 min. Therefore, diclofenac is placed within the OTrAMS Box 1 applicability domain, indicating the highest level of confidence in the estimation. Diclofenac was initially identified at level 4 because it did not have an automatically triggered MSMS spectrum, but after processing, samples were reanalysed in the MSMS mode, and the feature that was tentatively identified as diclofenac was prioritized for fragmentation. This approach helped to transfer diclofenac to level 2a (MSMS score – 943.3) and put it into the priority list of chemicals that are to be confirmed with analytical standards. This example demonstrates the effectiveness of incorporating the TTR-binding assay suspect list into the workflow, and its synergistic combination with predictive tools. In fraction 66, the hypertension drug candesartan, the azo dye aminoazobenzene, and a major metabolite of the calcium channel inhibitor amlodipine (O-des[2-aminoethyl]-O-carboxymethyl dehydroamlodipine) were identified at level 3 (positive mode). Candesartan was also annotated at level 5 in the negative mode given its mass deviation >5 ppm (5.54 ppm) (despite having a high MSMS score of 881). Fraction 66 also contained two other substances from the suspect list, i.e. the NSAID fenoprofen and the

Fig. 2. Bioassay responses to the unfractionated (A1-B1) and fractionated (A2-B2) extracts. A – FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay, B – AFB bioassay, PB – procedural blank, WW – well water, SW – surface water. The asterisk for fractions 4 and 5 (Figure A2) means that the response for those fractions was set at 100 % as fluorescence quenching was observed for FITC-T4. The asterisk for fraction 4 (Figure B2) means that the response in this fraction was set at 100 % as high inhibition of the luminescence was observed for the PB.

bisphenol-A replacement bisphenol-S. The MSMS spectrum of the tentative fenoprofen feature, however, was completely different from the library spectrum of fenoprofen. For bisphenol-S the predicted $t_R=10.73$ min deviated substantially from the experimental $t_R=15.18$ min of the tentative candidate.

Fatty acids docosahexanoic acid (fractions 81 and 82) and palmitic acid (fractions 82 and 83) were identified at level 3. Palmitic acid was also on the TTR-suspect list. A manual examination of the MSMS spectra of palmitic acid (Fig S19) showed no fragmentation at the applied collision energy (CE), consistent with data from the EU Mass Bank. This characteristic was later used for the manual search for features with a similar lack of fragmentation pattern. In fraction 84 the plasticizer di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate was identified (positive mode) at level 2a and the phthalates substitute dioctyl adipate (positive mode) at level 5 given its mass deviation >5 ppm (-5.36 ppm) (despite a high MSMS score of 842.8).

In the active fractions of WW, palmitic acid was identified in fractions 82 and 83 at level 2a in negative mode and insect-repellent diethyltoluamide (DEET) in fractions 64 and 65 in positive mode. All the feature tables of the active fractions for the tested samples can be found in the supplementary [Excel S3 and S4 files](#).

Based on the AFB bioassay, the catalyst for flexible polyester foams 4,4'-(oxydiethylene)bis(morpholine) was identified (positive mode) at level 2a in fractions 4 and 5. In fractions 70 and 71, the flavouring agent N-ethyl-4-menthane-3-carboxamide was identified (positive mode) at level 3. Vanillin azine, 2,4-octanedione, 3,5-dimethyl adamantane carboxylic acid, N-octanoic acid, 4-N-butylcyclohexylethanoic acid (all positive mode) and zearalenone (negative mode) were also annotated in fractions 70 and 71 due to a match with the AFB bioassay suspect list. However, based on the RTI platform data, only a few compounds were selected for further investigation: the active pharmaceutical ingredient intermediate 3,5-dimethyl adamantane carboxylic acid (experimental $t_R=16.33$ min, predicted $t_R=15.70$ min), the fragrance ingredient 4-N-

butylcyclohexylethanoic acid (which tentatively eluted in two peaks with $t_{R1}=16.42$ min and $t_{R2}=16.55$ min, predicted $t_R=16.44$ min), and the mycotoxin zearalenone (experimental $t_R=16.31$ min, predicted $t_R=15.48$ min). All these compounds fall within the OTrAMS Box 1 domain according to the RTI platform. In fractions 80 and 81 lysophospholipid lysophosphatidylethanolamine LPE 18:1 (O-LysoPE) was identified (negative mode) at level 2a. In fraction 81, fatty acid eicosapentaenoic acid was identified (negative mode) and had a high MSMS score of 854, but its mass deviation >5 ppm (5.72 ppm) caused it to be identified at level 5 only. 2-Pyrrolidinone (positive mode) and 2,6,10-trimethylundecanoic acid (negative mode) were also annotated in fractions 80 and 81 due to a match with the AFB bioassay suspect list. According to the retention time predictions from the RTI platform, only 2,6,10-trimethylundecanoic acid, with an experimental $t_R=18.68$ min and a predicted $t_R=18.81$ min, is categorized within the OTrAMS Box 1 domain.

To find additional possible candidates that were neither annotated with the libraries, nor with the TTR-binding and AFB bioassays suspect lists, CECscreen annotations were manually reviewed. One of the candidates in positive ESI, which was annotated from CECscreen (level 4) in fraction 73, was trifloxystrobin acid ($t_R=16.84$ min), a metabolite of the fungicide trifloxystrobin. Based on the RTI platform and the LC-separation conditions employed, the predicted retention time for trifloxystrobin acid ($t_R=17.75$ min) falls within the OTrAMS Box 1 domain, indicating high confidence. The extract was subsequently re-analyzed, including the suspected precursor ion of trifloxystrobin acid. The recorded MSMS spectrum corresponded with the fragmentation spectrum of trifloxystrobin acid in the EU MassBank, achieving an MSMS score of 948.7 (level 2a).

Palmitic acid, identified at level 3, exhibited no fragmentation upon manual inspection of its spectra. Consequently, other features in the active fractions with similar fragmentation patterns were manually examined. At a retention time of 18.8 min, a feature annotated by

CECscreen was detected, with palmitoleic acid (level 4*) as one of the possible candidates. According to the RTI platform, the predicted retention time for this feature was 19.66 min, placing it within the high-confidence Box 1 domain.

3.4. Chemical confirmations of the identified compounds

4-Aminoazobenzene, candesartan, diclofenac, trifloxystrobin acid, 6:2 FTSA, PFOA, docosahexaenoic acid, palmitoleic acid, palmitic acid, di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate, dioctyl adipate, 4,4'-(oxydiethylene)bis(morpholine), N-ethyl-4-menthane-3-carboxamide, gamma-dodecalactone, zearalenone and eicosapentaenoic acid were prioritized for the confirmation based on the automatic identifications, in-silico predictions, manual identifications and availability of the reference standards. All the compounds tested were successfully confirmed (Section 2.7), except gamma-dodecalactone, dioctyladipate and zearalenone. Table 1 presents a summary of the confidence levels associated with the identifications.

Comparative MSMS head-to-tail spectra of the identified compounds and reference standards are presented in Figures S8-S23. The retention time and MSMS spectrum of gamma-dodecalactone (Figure S12), differed from the tentative candidate. Although the MSMS spectra of the dioctyl adipate reference standard and the tentative candidate were very similar, the retention time of dioctyl adipate was observed to be 0.24 min higher ($t_R=19.53$ min) than that of the candidate. Given this retention time difference, it was speculated that the compound in question was diethylhexyl adipate rather than dioctyl adipate. This was later confirmed when the reference standard of diethylhexyl adipate matched exactly in retention time and MSMS spectrum with the tentative candidate (Figure S23). The experimental retention time of zearalenone was 16.15 min, which was 0.16 min lower than that observed in SW ($t_R=16.31$ min). Since the intensity of the feature was very low, it was not possible to obtain the MSMS spectrum for this feature, thus leaving it at level 3. The presence of 6:2 FTSA, branched, and linear PFOA in the extracts was additionally confirmed by the in-house routine method for the PFAS analysis, based on ISO 21,675 (ISO 21675 2019). Semi-quantitative concentrations (Table 2) were estimated only for the compounds with a notable concentration-dependent response in the respective bioassays (Section 3.5).

3.5. Bioassay confirmation of chemically confirmed compounds

In the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay, 4-aminoazobenzene, diclofenac, trifloxystrobin acid, 6:2 FTSA, PFOA, docosahexaenoic acid, palmitoleic acid, palmitic acid, and di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate demonstrated clear concentration-dependent responses (Fig. 3). The concentration-response curve of di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate levelled off at 60 % remaining FITC-T4 binding, due to the limited solubility of this compound at high concentrations. IC_{20} values are shown in Table 2. At the highest test concentration, candesartan (89 μ M) only caused a 28 % inhibition of FITC-T4 binding to TTR, and diethylhexyl adipate (27 μ M) showed no inhibition at all. Based on these weak TTR-binding potencies, the contributions of these compounds to the total TTR-binding potency of the fractions were further ignored.

To exclude that the decreased FITC-T4 binding activity in the presence of fatty acids was due to surface activity leading to reduced FITC-T4 availability in the binding assay, the critical micelle concentration (CMC) of palmitic acid was determined under the conditions of the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay measurements. Details of the experiments are described in Section S2.1. It was demonstrated that palmitic acid does not form micelles in the range of concentrations causing decreased TTR-binding by FITC-T4, not even at the highest test concentration (79 μ M).

In the AFB bioassay, eicosapentaenoic acid demonstrated a clear concentration-dependent response (Fig. 4). 4,4'-(oxydiethylene)bis(morpholine) showed no response, not even at the highest test concentration (169 μ M). Zearalenone showed a concentration-dependent

response but, as mentioned above (Section 3.4), was only identified at level 3.

3.6. Contributions to the bioassay response

Calculation of the contributions of the confirmed compounds to the bioassay response of the fractions was performed according to Section 2.8 taking into account IC_{20} values and semi-quantitative concentrations from Table 2. As WW contained almost no bio-active fractions, calculations were performed for SW only.

As evident in Table 3, the confirmed compounds in some fractions explain a considerable part of the observed bioassay response. For fraction 82, the explained response even goes beyond 100 %, which might be attributed to the loss of palmitoleic acid during the evaporation step of the fractionated plates and semi-quantitative concentration determination. However, in the cases of fractions 66 and 84, the confirmed compounds only explain a minor part of the response, indicating the need for additional examination of the features within these fractions. In the future, the application of the MLinvitrotox framework (Arturi and Hollender, 2023), trained on the newly developed TTR-binding database, could provide a beneficial approach for further investigation of the active fractions. Moreover, exploring alternative ionization sources for the LC-HRMS instrument, such as Atmospheric Pressure Chemical Ionization or Atmospheric Pressure Photoionization, represents another potential direction for the further research.

3.7. Overview of the identified chemicals and their PMT/vPvM assessment

The PMT assessment of the identified bioactive substances was performed according to the vPvM/PMT criteria accepted for EU CLP regulation, as described in Section 2.9. According to this classification, T assignment cannot be made based on a compound's activity in the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay or AFB bioassay alone. However, the activity of the identified substances in these bioassays may indicate their T potential. Also, given the bioactive nature of the active compounds, their likelihood of possessing properties suitable for T classification is high. The substances identified belong to different chemical classes, some of which are already known to be hazardous to human health and the environment. Since the applied MSPE procedure proved capable of isolating M/vM substances (Table S1), most of the identified substances were vM and turned out to be P/vP and T. The rationale for the PMT/vPvM assessment of these compounds is summarized in the supplementary Excel S5 file.

The identified fatty acids palmitic acid, palmitoleic acid, eicosapentaenoic acid, and docosahexaenoic acid did not meet the criteria for PMT/vPvM. As fatty acids are generally considered safe and are naturally occurring substances that are part of a balanced diet, further attention will focus on compounds that did meet the PMT/vPvM criteria and may pose a more serious risk for human or environmental health.

4-Aminoazobenzene (potential PMT/vPvM) belongs to the class of azo compounds as well as aromatic amines. It was historically used in the production of dyes and pigments. Azo dyes, and by extension compounds like 4-aminoazobenzene, have been a subject of concern in toxicology due to their potential to form carcinogenic amines. These concerns are particularly relevant when these compounds are metabolized in the human body, where they can be reduced to form aromatic amines, compounds known for their carcinogenic potential (Chung, 2016). Some compounds within this class, such as 3,3'-dichlorobenzidine and 2,4-diaminoanisole sulfate, have been reported to induce thyroid-related tumours in rats (Chung, 2016). These include thyroid follicular cell adenomas, thyroid follicular cell carcinomas, malignant thyroid follicular cell tumours, and thyroid C-cell adenomas or carcinomas (Chung, 2016).

Diclofenac (PMT & vPvM), a well-known NSAID, is primarily used for its effectiveness in reducing pain and inflammation in various

Table 1

Overview of the features identified in active fractions of SW extract from the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay and the AFB bioassay. The presence of compounds in two different fractions implies their retention times are within the error margin of adjacent fractions, as detailed in Section S1.1. The information in brackets for the columns "level 1" and "rejected" shows the level of identification before the confirmation and the presence of annotation in the suspect list, the number in the columns "level 4*", "level 4" and "level 5" shows the number of annotated features from the CECscreen suspect list.

FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay									
ESI Polarity	Fraction	Level 1	Level 2a	Level 3	Level 4* (n)	Level 4 (n)	Level 5 (n)	Rejected	
Pos	65				5	26	138		
	66	4-Aminoazobenzene (3) Candesartan (3)		Amlodipine metabolite	3	15	165		
	72	Diclofenac (2a, TTR SL)			6	26	333		
	73	Diclofenac (2a, TTR SL) Trifloxystrobin acid (2a, <i>in silico</i>)			1	27	174	Nonylphenol (5, TTR SL)	
	81				1	20	213		
	82				1	27	232		
	83				0	15	199		
	84	Di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (2a) Di(2-ethylhexyl)adipate (5)			1	17	154	Diocetyl adipate (5)	
	Neg	65				4	11	69	Bisphenol S (5, TTR SL) Fenoprofen (5, TTR SL)
		66	Candesartan (5)			7	23	167	Bisphenol S (5, TTR SL) Fenoprofen (4, TTR SL)
72		Diclofenac (2a, TTR SL)			3	15	57		
73		Diclofenac (2a, TTR SL) 6:2 Fluorotelomer sulfonic acid (3, TTR SL) Perfluorooctanoic acid (2, TTR SL)			8	16	43		
81		Palmitoleic acid (4*, <i>in silico</i>) Docosahexaenoic acid (3)			6	14	33		
82		Palmitoleic acid (4*, <i>in silico</i>) Docosahexaenoic acid (3) Palmitic acid (3, TTR SL)			8	13	30		
83		Palmitic acid (3, TTR SL)			4	5	26		
84					1	12	29		
AFB bioassay									
ESI Polarity		Fraction		Level 2a	Level 3	Level 4* b (n)	Level 4 (n)	Level 5 (n)	
Pos	4	4,4'-(Oxydiethylene)bis(morpholine) (2a)			2	3	26		
	5	4,4'-(Oxydiethylene)bis(morpholine) (2a)			6	13	30		
	70	N-Ethyl-4-menthane-3-carboxamide (3)			2	7	161	Vanillin azine (4*, AFB SL) 2,4-Octanedione (4, AFB SL) 3,5-Dimethyl adamantane carboxylic acid (5, AFB SL)	
	71	N-Ethyl-4-menthane-3-carboxamide (3)		2,2'-(Tetradecylimino) diethanol	1	12	332	Vanillin azine (4*, AFB SL) 2,4-Octanedione (4, AFB SL) 3,5-Dimethyl adamantane carboxylic acid (5, AFB SL) N-octanoic acid (4, AFB SL) 4-N-butylcyclohexylethanoic acid (4*, AFB SL) gamma-dodecalactone (3)	
	80				3	14	139	2-Pyrrolidinone (5, AFB SL)	
Neg	81				1	20	213	2-Pyrrolidinone (5, AFB SL)	
	4				0	1	5		
	5				0	0	7		
	70			Zearalenone (3, AFB SL)	3	12	48		
	71			Zearalenone (3, AFB SL)	3	13	47		
	80		O-LysoPE		4	10	23		
81	Docosahexaenoic acid (3) Eicosapentaenoic acid (5)		O-LysoPE		7	21	44		

Table 2

IC₂₀ values in the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay and AFB bioassay and semi-quantitative concentrations in SW extract.

FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay				
Compound	IC ₂₀ , uM	RP	Semi-quantitative concentration in the well of the fractionated plate ² , (uM)	Semi-quantitative concentration in SW ³ , (nM)
Thyroxine (T4)	0.011	1	NA ¹	NA ¹
4-Aminoazobenzene	0.810	0.014	0.020	0.083
Diclofenac	0.201	0.057	0.076	0.316
Trifloxystrobin acid	1.271	0.009	0.004	0.017
6:2 FTSA	1.995	0.006	0.002	0.007
PFOA	0.089	0.128	Tentative branched PFOA 0.00013	Tentative branched PFOA 0.0006
Docosahexaenoic acid	0.444	0.026	0.017	0.072
Palmitoleic acid	0.316	0.036	0.490	2.050
Palmitic acid	0.249	0.046	1.360	5.667
Di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate	1.335	0.009	0.048	0.200

AFB bioassay				
Compound	IC ₂₀ , uM	RP	Semi-quantitative concentration in the well of the fractionated plate ² , (uM)	Semi-quantitative concentration in SW ³ , (nM)
Triclosan	1.480	1	NA ¹	NA ¹
Eicosapentaenoic acid	0.190	7.770	0.120	0.250

¹ thyroxine (T4) and triclosan were tested as reference compounds for the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay and the AFB bioassay, respectively.

² assuming that the compound elutes in only one single well.

³ concentrations with a median 60 % SPE recovery (Figure S7).

Fig. 3. Dose-response curves of the confirmed substances in FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay.

conditions, including arthritic disorders and acute musculoskeletal issues. Diclofenac's ecotoxicological impact is profound and widespread, affecting a diverse range of organisms (Sathishkumar et al., 2020). It was reported that exposure to diclofenac significantly decreased T4 levels and altered gene expression within the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis in zebrafish embryos/larvae (Wang et al., 2022).

Trifloxystrobin acid (PMT & vPvM) is a transformation product of

trifloxystrobin (Menger and Boström, 2023; Menger et al., 2021), which is a strobilurin-type fungicide that is widely used in agriculture to control a variety of fungal diseases. It was shown that exposure to trifloxystrobin significantly reduced the levels of thyroid hormones T3 and T4 in zebrafish (Cang et al., 2023), highlighting its potential to disrupt the endocrine system by influencing thyroid hormone balance. Additionally, the study (Cang et al., 2023) observed a decrease in the

Fig. 4. Dose-response curves of the confirmed substance (eicosapentaenoic acid) and zearalenone (identified at level 3) in AFB bioassay.

Table 3

Contributions of the confirmed substances to the total response of the bioactive fractions. Potencies are expressed as T4 bioanalytical equivalent concentration (BEQ T4). BEQ_{chem} was calculated by multiplying the semi-quantified concentration of a compound with its relative TTR-binding potency compared to T4, BEQ_{bio} was determined by interpolating the observed TTR-binding potency of the fraction into the T4 calibration curve. BEQ concentrations are expressed in nM in the bioassay, and should be divided by $REF=400$ (FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay) and $REF=800$ (AFB bioassay) to obtain the concentration in SW.

FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay				
Compound	BEQ_{chem} (T4), nM	Total BEQ_{chem} (T4), nM	Fraction BEQ_{bio} (T4), nM	Explained response, %
<i>Fraction 66 - 80.3 % FITC-T4 bound to TTR (% control)</i>				
4-aminoazobenzene	0.28	0.28	11.05	2.55
<i>Fraction 73 - 80.7 % FITC-T4 bound to TTR (% control)</i>				
Diclofenac	4.31	4.37	10.72	40.78
Trifloxystrobin acid	0.03			
6:2 FTSA	0.01			
PFOA	0.02			
<i>Fraction 82 - 78 % FITC-T4 bound to TTR (% control)</i>				
Palmitoleic acid	17.68	18.11	13.50	134.18
Docosahexenoic acid	0.44			
<i>Fraction 83 - 51 % FITC-T4 bound to TTR (% control)</i>				
Palmitic acid	62.27	62.27	74.20	83.92
<i>Fraction 84 - 76.8 % FITC-T4 bound to TTR (% control)</i>				
Di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate	0.41	0.41	14.83	2.76
AFB bioassay				
Compound	BEQ_{chem} (Triclosan), μ M	Total BEQ_{chem} (Triclosan), μ M	Fraction BEQ_{bio} (Triclosan), μ M	Explained response, %
<i>Fraction 81 - 70.8 % Luminescence (% control)</i>				
Eicosapentaenoic acid	0.93	0.93	1.86	50.12

expression of the deiodinase enzyme, crucial for managing thyroid hormone levels.

PFOA and 6:2 FTSA (both PMT & vPvM) are both part of a large group of man-made chemicals known as PFAS. These chemicals are very stable and don't interact much with other chemicals, making them useful in creating products that resist oils, stains, water, and heat. Epidemiological studies have identified associations between exposure to specific PFAS and various health effects, including effects on thyroid hormone system functioning (Fenton et al., 2021). Apart from T4 displacement from TTR (Weiss et al., 2009), in vitro studies have further indicated that PFAS have interfered with TH synthesis through inhibition of iodine uptake by the sodium-iodine symporter (NIS) and of iodination of tyrosine residues in thyroglobulin formation by thyroperoxidase (TPO) (Coperchini et al., 2021). Animal model studies have confirmed the thyroid-disrupting effects of PFAS, showing changes in circulating thyroid hormone levels, primarily through increased metabolic clearance rate (Coperchini et al., 2021). Notably, PFAS accumulation in the placentas of pregnant mice suggests potential alterations in thyroid hormone levels that could affect fetal development (Coperchini et al., 2021).

Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (vP, T, but not M) is a phased out global

environmental pollutant commonly used as a plasticizer in many products, particularly in medical devices, furniture materials, cosmetics, and personal care products. Due to its widespread use and the fact that di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate is noncovalently bound to plastics, it can leach out of these products, leading to environmental pollution and potential human exposure through inhalation, ingestion, and dermal contact. It disrupts the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis, affects the synthesis and metabolism of TH, and alters the expression of thyroid hormone receptors (Zhang et al., 2021).

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrates the successful application of EDA using the FITC-T4 TTR-binding assay and AFB bioassay for the identification of bioactive substances, including vPvM & PMT substances in surface water samples. The adapted MSPE method effectively concentrated a diverse range of chemicals including polar chemicals that may reach drinking water sources, and was compatible with the assays used in the EDA workflow. The creation of the TTR-binding database and suspect list significantly enhanced the identification process, particularly exemplified by diclofenac's identification as a primary contributor to

the bioactivity of the fraction. As a result of the study, fatty acids (4 acids) (not PMT/vPvM), di(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (not PMT/vPvM), 4-aminoazobenzene (potential PMT & vPvM), diclofenac (PMT & vPvM), trifloxystrobin acid (PMT & vPvM), 6:2 FTSA (PMT & vPvM) and PFOA (PMT & vPvM) were identified and confirmed in the active fractions. The confirmed substances, displaying varying potency levels in the assays, largely explained the observed bioactivity in the fractions. The EDA approach taken in this study makes a substantial contribution to environmental monitoring of bioactive persistent and mobile substances in aquatic media, and contribute crucially to their identification and hazard assessments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Timur Baygildiev: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Jeroen Meijer:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Data curation. **Peter Cenijn:** Investigation. **Marcel Riegel:** Resources. **Hans Peter H. Arp:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Marja Lamoree:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Timo Hamers:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

All data are available in 6 supplementary files. Additional raw data are available upon request.

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